

INTEGRATING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AND LANGUAGE SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP)

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Teaching English language for specific purposes is still a field in which new venues and perspectives are unfolding. Innovations have been driven so far because of new knowledge and proliferations of integrated instructional models. The focus is no longer on grammar but using language as a means of connecting with others around the world. That is because the purpose of learning languages has changed towards intercultural communication. This field is more learner-centered, more collaborative and driven by technology which supplies English language in authenticity and literacy. Thus, in this paper we aim at showing the most effective ways of teaching English for Specific Purposes through textbooks which should contain job-related English lessons which can be effectively taught through the means of new technology and extracurricular supplementary activities. As ESP professionals, we must be ready to develop courses that teach authentic language from many different fields, based on accurate needs analysis and appropriate materials and methodologies.

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Teaching English for Specific Purposes is different from teaching English as a foreign language. While the latter has to do with four essential skills to our students, like reading, listening, speaking and writing, in teaching English for Specific Purposes learners concentrate especially on vocabulary, language in the context, thus, it is related to the students' interests. In such situations, students may be taught a combination of skills which combines subject matter and language learning. Students

in English for specific purposes classrooms may be more motivated because their interest is to improve their abilities in the English language in a certain field, learn faster and be able to interact with speakers in their work.

Integrating authentic materials with language skills when teaching English for Specific Purposes is not an easy task. Instructors may face several challenges, starting from the selection of materials which should be appropriate to the objectives of the curriculum, to the implementation of those materials and their adaption in the classroom to meet the students' needs. Many instructors may be dissuaded from using authentic materials because they require an investment of time and preparing those materials requires longer time frames and more complex designs and they should meet especially the program's learning objectives. Even though, Internet has become an increasingly useful tool and indispensable to any instructor, making a selection of materials from one million pages that are added everyday proves difficult. In selecting the materials, the instructor needs to consider at least three basic aspects of the trainees' backgrounds:

1. Linguistic
2. Conceptual
3. Cultural

Linguistic background influences classroom management, the selection of tasks, the sequencing and execution of tasks, and the focus of microskill instruction (such as pronunciation and accent reduction). Conceptual (or knowledge) background determines the need for specificity or generality of information in the selected materials. Cultural background affects trainee-instructor interaction, the formality or informality of classroom interaction, and expectations of traditional instructor and trainee/student roles [2].

When teaching English for Specific purposes teachers should help students attain the skills needed, achieve their purposes and/or meet their expectations. In these courses, English should be presented not as the subject to be learned in isolation, but it should be presented in authentic contexts to make the learners to make the learners acquainted with the particular ways in which language is used in their fields of specialty or job-related situations. It is significant for the teacher to establish a positive learning environment in the classroom, must listen to them carefully,

answer their questions and as we said earlier present the language in authentic contexts where the students have some contact with the real language, e.g. through cassettes, conversation with native speakers, observation and other real situations.

Nunan and Miller define authentic materials as those which “were not created or edited expressly for language learners. Authentic materials illustrate how English is used naturally by native speakers” [5]. This means that most everyday objects in the target language can be qualified as authentic materials can be used not only for general English but for ESP learning/teaching as well. There are unlimited authentic resources which can be included in ESP courses starting from day to day objects, like business cards, banks leaflets, photographs, receipts, catalogues, currency, reports, financial statements, instructions, banks accounts, application forms, pictures, registration forms, letters/emails, diagrams, agreements, brochures, newspapers, journals, TV and radio broadcast, films documentaries, internet websites, general or special literature, authentic specialist publications in the field, statistics, reports, surveys, etc.

Today easily accessible websites can help students to find relevant authentic task-based materials. The role of the learner as the text provider in this case is important because in the day to day learning/teaching the exposure to authentic materials can make the task more interesting and motivating. The Internet search provides almost unlimited resources for profession-based or specific topics. The interaction online (e.g. the teacher searches for sites on a specific topic, makes questions, and posts the students online) can successfully replace authentic printed materials brought into the classroom and make the ESP classroom significantly livelier.

Anything can be used as authentic material, but from a practical/economical point of view, the most useful resource is the Internet, with large amounts of different text types, language styles, and videos of interviews that cannot be found in textbooks which become very dated and do not include improper English. The variety of internet-based text types means that it is easier to find something that will interest the learner and may even encourage for further reading, listening or watching. It can also promote other skills such as skimming/scanning, extensive/intensive reading, summary, essay, email writing, outlining, mapping,

sorting, adding information and may result in oral performance, such as newscasts, conversations, interviews, presentations, lectures, reports, etc. The resources of authentic spoken English may stimulate and maintain motivation, especially if the activity does not require identifying or producing every word and when control is transferred from teachers to students by giving ESP students access to technologies.

Furthermore, authenticity has been pointed to by various authors as a relevant feature in ESP methodology and thus, authentic materials constitute an aspect traditionally emphasized in the ESP literature. The learner-centered approach is essential to ESP teaching, and identified learner's needs are not fully satisfied by published texts. These authentic materials should be taken from the real world, as mentioned above, and not primarily created for pedagogical reasons. Such materials are particularly important for communicative purposes since they reproduce an immersion environment and provide a realistic context for tasks that relate to learner's needs. Students and teachers can use authentic materials as a means to "link the formal, and to some extent artificial, environment of the classroom with the real world in which we hope our students will eventually be using the language they are learning [3].

It is true that authentic materials and realia are often found in ESP course books today. They can increase students' motivation and expose them to real language and culture as well as to the different genres of the professional community they want to be part of. However, such materials should constantly be updated, edited in order to be a suitable match between learner and material learned. Fortunately, ESP learners are not typically beginners in the foreign language, and authentic materials provide a good setting for introducing roughly-tuned input in a comprehensible way.

Reppen highlights the fact that, in recent years, many ELT professionals have expressed a preference for authentic materials in their lessons, using language from natural texts instead of ready-made examples. In this sense, such corpora provide "a ready resource of natural, or authentic, texts for language learning". ESP students may not be aware that they are using corpus based products, but in fact they are. When designing a special purpose corpus, in order to ensure that it contains authentic LSP material, Bowker and Pearson recommend that the author of each text should be an acknowledged subject-field expert. That means that ESP

professionals have to spend lots of time preparing and adapting authentic materials for use in the classroom so that they are easy and meaningful to the students [3].

Authentic materials are divided into two categories: materials which contain language and materials which stimulate the production of language [3]. There are mainly three functions that authentic texts serve in ESP courses: First, using authentic materials from the learners' work environment to the classroom and the teachers offers assistance. Second, the ESP teachers always look for texts that are as close to the learners' target situations in their jobs as possible. Third, authentic texts serve as sources of information for the teacher and may already be collected during the needs analysis period. Offering the students assistance by introducing authentic texts in ESP courses avoids the use of certain texts in language teaching materials which bear little resemblance to the genuine target discourse samples learners encounter in the world outside the classroom. Thus, the combination of availability and relevance makes their learning process more meaningful. There is a drawback even when take-away format is available online, since these materials can become obsolete very quickly and it is time-consuming to the teacher finding new samples of authentic texts for ESP lessons which will be exploited for a short period of time. Involving learners in the production of their own authentic materials can solve this problem especially when the students work in close cooperation with their teachers. When this happens, subject-experts can act as facilitators and consultants and their task will be to assist the ESP teacher to select authentic texts and tasks [3].

Given the fact that the ESP teacher is often not an expert in the specific field of his/her students, it is paramount that the degree of authenticity of the textbook match the teacher's preparation. It must be borne in mind that the textbook is a mere instrument or tool which the teacher should be able to adapt to his/her specific context in order to match the needs of the learners. The organization of the topics or units also needs to be reflected upon. In this sense, it is advisable to build lessons around content-based themes in the specific purpose area. As Schleppegrell recommends using a thematic organization that chooses particular topics and builds on them from one class to another, rather than random texts or unrelated topics. Understand that in "authentic" situations, understanding a new text comes from reference to the context and surroundings. Build such

contexts into your units by referring to previous work and drawing on the frame of reference that learners already have [1].

A number of criteria need to be considered in selecting authentic texts for classroom use according to McGrath are: a) relevance (to syllabus, to learners, needs), b) intrinsic interest of topic/theme (interest learners), c) cultural appropriateness (religiously, social, political), d) linguistic demands (language proficiency), e) cognitive demands (maturity and knowledge), f) logistical consideration: e.g. length, legibility/audibility, g) quality (as a model for use or as a representative token of a text-type), and h) exploitability. For the ESP situation, we must also consider whether the goals are set are authentic with regard to students' real-world roles, and whether the goals set are authentic tasks or activities that take place in the learning situation are authentic. In material development for ESP, Moore [4] suggests six criteria to be applied in creating materials:

Purpose: Is the purpose clearly defined?

Type: Does the exercise type effectively and economically accomplish the purpose?

Content: Is the ratio of language given and student task economic? Are instructions to students clear?

Interest: Is it interesting?

Authentic: Is it a meaningful task? Is it challenging?

Difficulty: Does it contain distracting difficulties?

Through authentic texts, learners would be exposed to the cultural force of the language that they are learning and so comprehension and perceptions of the language would improve. Graves (2000) and Tomlinson (2011) [4] describe basic principles of second language acquisition that directly relevant to the development, selection and use of language materials and activities. These also reflect beliefs about how people learn in general and what the teacher's role should be in using materials. Some of these principles are presented below [4]:

Learner affect

- Materials should achieve impact
- Materials should help learners feel at ease

- Materials should take into account that learners differ in affective attitudes
- Materials should help learners to develop confidence
- What is being taught should be perceived by learners as relevant and useful

Learner engagement

- Materials should require and facilitate learner engagement and self-investment
- Materials should allow students to problem solve, discover and analyze
- The learner's attention should be drawn to linguistic features of the input
- Materials should provide variety: in roles and groupings, in type and purpose
- Materials should provide the learners with opportunities to use the target language to achieve meaningful communicative purposes

Learner Styles and Preferences

- Materials should take into account that learners differ in learning styles
- Materials should allow students the opportunity to progress at their own rate
- Materials should not rely too much on controlled practice, but allow for creative use of language and learning through trial and error

Learner Needs and Development

- Materials should draw on what students know (their experiences)
- Materials should focus on (authentic) language needs outside of the classroom and expose the learners to language in authentic use
- Learners must be ready to acquire points being presented in the materials
- Materials should provide opportunities for outcome feedback
- Materials should take into account that positive effects of instruction are usually delayed
- Materials should help students develop specific skills and strategies

Conclusions

While ESP teachers can and should draw on a wide variety of

published materials for their classes, it is essential that they know how to identify, adapt, and develop materials to address the specific language needs they have identified for their students. Using technology is a good opportunity for learners to find authentic texts and develop proficiency in ESP language studies. The benefit of using a variety of authentic materials and text types are many because it helps learners absorb a very specific vocabulary, language styles and authentic spoken English. Technology and other authentic resources promote a more active approach to autonomous and constructive learning.

References

1. CAÑADO, María Luisa Pérez; ESTEBAN, Ana Almagro (2007) - *Authenticity in the Teaching of ESP: An Evaluation Proposal*.
2. DUMITRESCU, Valeriu (2000) – *Authentic materials-Selection and implementation in exercise language training*, English teaching forum, p. 21-24.
3. TORREGROSA, G. B., PENAMARIA S.S. (2011) - *Use of authentic Materials in the ESP classroom*, Encuentro 20, Colegio Diocesano-Avila, Universidad de Salamanca, p. 89-94
4. UPTON, Thomas A.: *Current issues in ESP materials*, Indiana University Purdue University Indianapolis, U.S.A.
5. VAICIUNIENE, V. UZPALIENE, D. (2010) - *Authentic resources in Technology-based ESP Learning*, in *Studies about languages*, 94-98.